

Urban Relief

Riga Pilot Report

D4.9

Document Factsheet

Grant agreement	101086638
Call identifier	Horizon-CL6-2022-Governance-01-08
Project title	Urban ReLeaf: Citizen-powered data ecosystems for inclusive and green urban transitions
Project start date	01/01/2023
Duration	48 months
Instrument	Horizon Europe
Type of action	Innovation action
Deliverable number	D4.9
Deliverable name	Riga Pilot Report
Work package	WP4: Mobilize participants and implement Urban ReLeaf city pilots
Task	T4.7: Riga: Adaptive community-based urban environment planning for the wellbeing of citizens
Deliverable lead	Riga Planning Region (RPR) & Riga City Council (RCC)
Deliverable type	Report
Due date	31/12/2025
Review completed	23/12/2025
Submission date	27/12/2025
Document version	1.0

Disclaimer

The content of this deliverable does not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission. Responsibility for the information and views expressed herein lies with the author(s). All Urban ReLeaf consortium members are committed to publish accurate and up to date information. However, the Urban ReLeaf consortium members cannot accept liability for any inaccuracies or omissions, nor do they accept liability for any direct, indirect, special, consequential, or other losses or damages of any kind arising out of the use of this information.

Copyright notice

This work by parties of the Urban ReLeaf consortium is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International License.

Acknowledgement

Funded by
the European Union

UK Research
and Innovation

Reference

Please cite this work as:

Skudra, S., Gagane, N. (2025). Riga Pilot Report. D4.9 4 for the Horizon Europe and Innovate UK co-funded project Urban ReLeaf under grant agreement IDs: 101086638, 10061290, and 10041792. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18015589

Deliverable name	Riga Pilot Report
Authors	Sabine Skudra (RPR)
Contributors	Nora Gagane (RPR, RCC), Georgios Grivas (NOA), Todd Harwell (IIASA)

Short description	Deliverable includes overall description and results of two campaigns – Air Quality Campaign titled “Adopt a sensor” ongoing for two years and second campaign titled “Step towards greener city” - one year campaign. Both campaigns we intend to continue in the final year of the project to keep communities together and to collect more data.
Keywords	Citizen science, community engagement, urban environment, air quality and heat islands, health and wellness, green infrastructure

Dissemination level		
PU	Public	X
SEN	Sensitive – limited under the conditions of the GA	
EU-R	Classified information - Restricted under EC Decision 2005/444	
EU-C	Classified information - Confidential under EC Decision 2005/444	

History			
Version	Date	Released by	Comment
0.1	03.10.2025	Sabine Skudra (RPR)	Draft version
0.2	12.12.2025	Sabine Skudra (RPR), Nora Gagane (RCC)	Updated draft version
0.3	16.12.2025	Todd Harwell (IIASA)	Contribution to section 2.5, review, and suggested edits
0.4	17.12.2025	Georgios Grivas (NOA)	Contribution to section 1.5, review, and suggested edits
0.5	22.12.2025	Sabine Skudra (RPR)	Updates and edits
1.0	27.12.2025	Todd Harwell (IIASA)	Final version for submission

Project Partners

Table of Contents

Table of Contents.....	4
Acronyms.....	5
List of Figures	6
List of Tables	7
Executive Summary	8
Background on the Urban ReLeaf Project and City Pilots	10
1 Air Quality Campaign	11
1.1 Context and Objectives.....	12
1.2 Design and Implementation	13
1.3 Areas of Focus and Technologies Used	14
1.4 Citizen Engagement and Data Collection.....	16
1.5 Findings and Reflections	18
1.6 Recommendations and Future Steps.....	23
2 Heat Stress Campaign.....	24
2.1 Context and Objectives.....	28
2.2 Design and Implementation	28
2.3 Areas of Focus and Technologies Used	30
2.4 Citizen Engagement and Data Collection.....	31
2.5 Findings and Reflections	33
2.6 Recommendations and Future Steps.....	39
Appendices	40
Appendix A: Open call for campaign “Adopt a sensor”.....	40
Appendix B: Application form to fill in to adopt an AQ sensor	42
Appendix C: Adopt a Sensor’ Success: Riga Engages Citizens in Air Quality Monitoring 48	
Appendix D: Press release and posters: Open call to become a researcher of heat islands	51
Appendix E: Application form to fill in to become a researcher of heat islands (TRH sensors)	55

Acronyms

AQ	Air Quality
AQI	Air Quality Index
EEA	European Environment Agency
NOA	National Observatory of Athens
NGO	Non-governmental Organisation
QA	Quality Assurance
QC	Quality Control
RPR	Riga Planning Region
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
TRH	Temperature and Humidity

AWAITING VALIDATION BY THE
EUROPEAN COMMISSION

List of Figures

Figure 1. Screenshot from online event / meeting with sensors adopters, May 2024.....	12
Figure 2. Screenshot from online event / meeting with sensors adopters, May 2024.....	12
Figure 3. Installation process of AQ sensors in 2024.....	15
Figure 4. Indicative PM2.5 sensor monitoring results from the Urban ReLeaf project (March 2024–March 2025), based on PurpleAir data (Source: Riga City Air Quality Improvement Action Program 2026–2030).	17
Figure 5. The installed PM2.5 sensor network, at 20 sites of different characterisation in Riga.	18
Figure 6. Distribution of PM2.5 concentrations in air quality categories for the annual measurement period in Riga. The assessment is based on calculated 24-hour rolling averages.	21
Figure 7. Mean annual PM2.5 concentrations per site type correlated with the urban area in a radius of 1 km around each site.	22
Figure 8. Heat Stress Campaign Launch event, June 16th, 2025.....	25
Figure 9. Guided tour in Sports Palace Gardens, July 16th, 2025.	25
Figure 10. A walk through the green courtyards, August 5th, 2025.	26
Figure 11. A walk through the green courtyards, August 5th, 2025.	26
Figure 12. A walk along the “Green String”, September 15th, 2025.....	27
Figure 13. Map of Riga city neighbourhoods.	30
Figure 14. Presentation in SATDISFACTION event.	32
Figure 15. Presentation in LIFE LATESTadapt event.	33
Figure 16. Spatial coverage of sensor measurements in Riga on a log scale.	34
Figure 17. Amount of data by device. (Counting a pair of relative humidity and temperature as one observation and ignoring the button records).....	34
Figure 18. All temperature measurements throughout the days, with the median line and the 25 and 75 quartiles for each hour shown.....	35
Figure 19. Example of a trip with dubious GPS records based on erratic measurements at the end of a trip, with speed in km/h.....	36
Figure 20. Participant ratings of the EcoPulse app (1-5 scale).	38
Figure 21. Participants' indication of willingness to participate in future Heat Stress Campaign activities.....	38

List of Tables

Table 1. Information about AQ monitors and installation sites.	19
Table 2. Descriptive statistics on the concentrations recorded by the AQ sensor monitoring network (16/20 installed sites) during the first year of full operation (September 2024 – August 2025).	21

AWAITING VALIDATION BY THE
EUROPEAN COMMISSION

Executive Summary

There were two citizen science campaigns implemented in the Riga pilot in 2024 and 2025. The first campaign lasted 2 years while the second lasted one year but both were diverse with approaches, results and lessons learned. Both campaigns yielded important experiences to develop further within the Urban ReLeaf project and in upcoming projects implemented in the Riga planning region.

Air Quality Campaign (Riga, 2024–2025) - "Adopt a sensor"

Purpose: Assess the role of greenspaces in reducing PM_{2.5} exposure and improving public health.

Approach:

- Installed 20 low-cost PurpleAir sensors across diverse sites (urban green, near-green, near-traffic, traffic) to complement two regulatory stations.
- Engaged citizens via "Adopt a Sensor" open call; strong volunteer response (40 applications).
- Developed partnerships with municipal institutions, educational organisations, and non-governmental organisations (NGOs).
- Initiated cooperation with Riga Digital Agency to create a citywide data visualisation platform.

Results:

- Over 87,000 mean observation hours collected in Year 1; indicative trends align with official monitoring.
- Urban greenspaces consistently linked to lower PM_{2.5} exposure, though not fully isolated from traffic/domestic emissions.
- No exceedances of EU short-term PM_{2.5} thresholds; annual averages suggest localized hotspots.
- Data supports arguments for low-emission zones and greening strategies in Riga.

Lessons Learned:

- Citizen engagement exceeded expectations; volunteers remain committed beyond campaign.
- Clear communication and technical readiness are critical for sustained participation.
- Expansion of sensor network and integration into city planning recommended.

Heat Stress Campaign (Riga, Summer 2025) "Step towards greener city"

Purpose: Raise awareness of urban heat islands and the role of greenery; involve citizens in temperature and relative humidity (TRH) data collection.

Approach:

- Distributed 54 TRH sensors; collected ~49,000 paired observations via EcoPulse app.
- Organised educational events and thematic walks to strengthen community engagement.
- Collaborated with related projects (LIFE LATESTadapt, SATSDIFACTION) for knowledge exchange.

Findings:

- Recorded temperatures ranged from 9.6°C to 40.2°C; mobile TRH sensors showed ~4.4°C higher readings than reference stations, confirming heat island effects.
- Data highlights cooling benefits of green spaces and need for improved urban design.
- Technical challenges with app usability affected participation; WhatsApp community support proved essential.

Lessons Learned:

- Citizen science is effective for awareness and data collection but requires user-friendly technology.
- Future campaigns should improve technical reliability, maintain strong communication, and explore gamification for motivation.

Strategic Impact and Next Steps

- Urban ReLeaf has strengthened Riga's capacity for data-driven environmental governance.
- Ongoing development of a citywide data visualisation platform will enable broader use of collected data.
- Recommendations include expanding sensor networks, improving citizen engagement strategies, and leveraging findings for greening plans and low-emission zones.
- Continued collaboration with EU projects and local stakeholders will ensure alignment with climate neutrality goals.

AWAITING VALIDATION BY THE
EUROPEAN COMMISSION

Background on the Urban ReLeaf Project and City Pilots

Urban ReLeaf promotes collaboration between local communities and public authorities to address urgent climate issues and support innovations that enable more just and green urban transitions. The project addresses the challenges of increasing environmental stresses in urban areas, accentuated inequalities in access to high-quality greenspace, lack of suitable data for planning and decision making as well as inclusion in public participation in science and research.

The main objectives of Urban ReLeaf are to:

- Understand current data ecosystem and urban greening and participation policies in six pilot cities and co-develop opportunities for citizen science and citizen participation to complement existing practices.
- Mobilise and empower local communities in issues of public interest surrounding urban green infrastructure and environmental stewardship.
- Support the long-term inclusion of active and passive data from citizens within official data streams for urban monitoring, planning and innovation in public policy.
- Encourage knowledge exchange and training across relevant actors beyond the six pilot cities by establishing a community of practice and an accelerator programme.
- Offer flexible and innovative ways of governance that can underpin inclusive green urban planning in support of the European Green Deal and UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

In pursuit of urban climate resilience, six Urban ReLeaf pilot cities co-create participatory, and data-driven innovations to democratise urban greenspace monitoring and the wider policy making process.

AWAITING VALIDATION BY THE
EUROPEAN COMMISSION

1 Air Quality Campaign

Campaign theme, approach, timeline, and key events

The Air Quality Campaign has been taking place in Riga during 2024 and 2025 and was focused on assessing the importance of green areas for reducing exposure of citizens to ambient fine particulate matter, thereby safeguarding public health and improving the quality of the urban environment. By involving diverse institutions and citizens, data were gathered to promote a general understanding about the actual air quality status in Riga, to underline the importance of a "green lifestyle", and to discuss what can be done, by each one of us and by all of us together, to improve situation step by step.

The first phase of the campaign in its first year focused on finding the best approach to installing sensors in the city of Riga, identifying and meeting relevant authorities and institutions, understanding technical requirements, publishing an open call to "adopt a sensor", and selecting participants. In the second phase, contracts were concluded with institutions and residents, and sensors were installed at five urban green (UG) areas, five near-green (NG) residential sites, eight near-traffic (NT) sites, and two traffic sites (T). One of these sensors was collocated with reference instrumentation at a regulatory monitoring site to support the field validation of measurements. In the third phase, when all sensors were installed, their operation was monitored, and analysis of the collected data began.

In the final phase of the first year of the campaign, the first results were received from the project partners and negotiations were initiated with the Riga Digital Agency on the development of a new data platform for the city. This platform is intended to display data from all sensors installed in the city, beginning with air quality data of the Urban ReLeaf project.

The second-year campaign focused on two topics: various educational activities for the community of residents and institutions involved in data collection, and cooperation with the Riga Digital Agency and other Riga city institutions to develop a data visualisation platform. Educational activities were implemented during events organised within the second campaign focused on heat stress. Still, cooperation was continued with the Riga Digital Agency and other Riga city institutions to design and develop a data visualisation platform and to exchange collected data (from sensors and from the Riga City air quality monitoring stations) till the end of the campaign.

Two online events were organised for the community of residents and institutions participating in data collection for the Air Quality Campaign. The first online event was organised in May 2024 to introduce the community to the project, the aims of the campaign, air pollution, and fine PM_{2.5} particles measured by Purple Air sensors that participants adopted in the planned campaign (Figure 1 and Figure 2).

The second online event for the community of residents and institutions participating in data collection for the Air Quality Campaign was organised in May 2025 to share results of the first year of the campaign, data gathered and analysed, and next steps.

Before the installation of these 20 low-cost air quality sensors in Riga, PM_{2.5} pollution was monitored by standard regulatory monitoring stations in only two locations: one in the city centre near the National Theatre and another further away in Bierīņi, near Akmens Garden Park.

Although these two stations provided valuable long-term data, there was a significant lack of spatial information extending down to the neighbourhood scale--particularly how air quality varies with proximity to greenspaces or heavily trafficked streets.

Figure 1. Screenshot from online event / meeting with sensors adopters, May 2024.

Figure 2. Screenshot from online event / meeting with sensors adopters, May 2024.

The installation of 20 new low-cost sensors has substantially reduced this data gap, providing a much more detailed spatial coverage of air quality across Riga. We were pleased that more than 87,000 mean observation hours were collected during the first year of operation. This two-year campaign has already helped to raise public awareness about the importance of air quality and will encourage further action to improve the urban environment.

1.1 Context and Objectives

The local challenges campaign addressed

Historically, Riga has faced problems related to exceedances of EU standards, particularly for nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) and particulate matter (PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}) and at roadside locations

impacted by intensive traffic. Actual concentrations of particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) in the air in Riga are comparable to those in other European capitals. However, most cities are making targeted improvements by modernizing transport and reducing traffic intensity through the introduction of low-emission zones. Such measures are also relevant in Riga. Therefore, wide spatial coverage of air quality monitoring, real-time data display, and air quality (AQ) assessment at different parts of the city can support a strong argument for faster and more targeted decision-making and improvements.

Connection to local, regional, national and EU priorities

Climate neutrality is one of the highest priorities across all levels of governance, and numerous important policy documents have been developed to achieve it. Similarly, the health and well-being of citizens, resource adequacy, and environmental quality are priorities for the European Union and its urban policies, similar to Riga. By regularly collecting data that reflects the parameters characterizing the quality of the urban environment, we can repeatedly evaluate and review the effectiveness of existing policies and actions, devise plans, and make data-driven decisions to inform new actions. On a city level, main strategic planning documents include the Riga Sustainable Development Strategy 2030 and the Riga Development Program for 2022–2027, both setting environmental quality and citizens wellbeing as very high priorities. To implement more exact actions, thematic policy documents have been developed or are in development, such as the Riga Greening plan, the Low emission zone, and the Air Quality action program.

The overarching objectives of the campaign

As part of the campaign, we focused more on air quality measurements in the city centre, where the intensity of construction is higher, and there are plans to introduce a low emission zone in the near future. We purposefully placed sensors in diverse areas including urban greenspaces, near-green locations, near-traffic residential areas and traffic sites to gain additional evidence of the significant contribution of urban greening activities in the urban environment and highlight the necessity of pollution reduction actions

1.2 Design and Implementation

Overall design of the campaign

The aim of installing air quality sensors, and engaging citizens in this process, was and still is to promote environmental awareness in the city and to underline the significance of green areas for air quality. Moreover, we are interested in renewing a discussion on the density of cars in the city centre including how much of the public outdoor space it takes up and how important the share of vehicular emissions is. Based on the assessment of these data, it will be possible to support data-driven discussions on the boundaries of the proposed low-emission zone in Riga. We remain committed to supporting the creation of a greener living environment for the residents of Riga city centre. The slogan for the first year of the campaign was “Adopt a Sensor” to recruit citizens, institutions and organisations to install sensors in their living or working space or in the building and open spaces for which environmental institutions are responsible.

Key partners and stakeholders involved

Twenty Urban ReLeaf sensors were available for the Air Quality Campaign in Riga, and all were installed by September 2024, with operation maintained throughout the second year (and will also continue until the end of the project and beyond). As part of the first year of the campaign, the open call “Adopt a Sensor” was organised, within the framework of which a successful cooperation with institutions and organisations was achieved, while also receiving 40 applications from residents volunteering to participate in the campaign by installing an air quality sensor at their workplace or residence. The sensors were adopted by various

representatives from municipal institutions, city parks, state, municipal and private educational institutions, and NGOs. Additional sensors were assigned to residents who applied through the open call and their locations fulfilled all siting criteria and technical requirements to ensure the validity and reliability of data. All selected monitoring sites were characterized by on-site visits, and special forms were filled in by RPR.

Strategies used to engage different target groups

Since the PurpleAir air quality sensors used in Urban ReLeaf require electricity and a Wi-Fi internet connection to operate, our initial plan was to coordinate their installation with the Riga Municipality departments responsible for lighting and green space management. However, installing sensors on city streets would require a complex process across several departments and incur additional costs. Therefore, we had to find alternative solutions for installation in the city centre. We continued our cooperation with the city park managing authority “Riga Forests” expanding our collaboration with various educational institutions and organised an open call for residents to install the remaining sensors and ensure good coverage in the city, thus initiating direct communication with the public about the project, its activities, and opportunities to get residents involved. Residents willing to install an air quality sensor at their residence or workplace were required to complete an extensive survey so that we could assess the suitability of the installation location and the participant’s commitment. We received 40 applications, from which we selected seven applications from private individuals, contacted these residents and invited them to participate in a first meeting, where we gathered all applicants, not only those selected, and shared information about the project, air quality and its importance for human health, as well as detailed technical information and practical instructions about the sensor installation.

In the first year of the campaign, the communication with residents was carried out through public releases and messages on social networks, as well as individual communication during the sensor installation process, concluding participation agreements, handing over the equipment and supervising their installation. In the second year of the campaign, activities were carried out in three main communication directions. The first direction focused on communication with the parties involved and an in-person workshop to move towards the creation of a single city sensor data platform where it would be possible to track the data of all sensors installed in the city. The platform is designed to be user-friendly, but also quite complex in order to meet the interests and needs of both residents and specialists. This activity is still ongoing and will continue next year in close cooperation with the Riga Digital Agency, which is developing this platform. The next communication with all applicants and wider cooperation was within the framework of our second campaign, which was dedicated to identifying heat islands in the city of Riga. We invited all applicants to an online event, where we shared the results of the first campaign focused on air quality and also talked about the opportunities to apply for participating in the TRH sensors. For the third communication direction, we continued with an open appeal and wide publicity in the social media about the project and the campaign planned for 2025, and citizen engagement activities. Accordingly, all further activities that were carried out and organised within the framework of the second campaign were also dedicated to air quality sensor users and those who applied to adopt the sensor.

1.3 Areas of Focus and Technologies Used

Geographic areas, neighbourhoods where the campaign was implemented

Considering the technical requirements and the fact that we only had 20 PurpleAir PA-II monitors (based on twin Plantower PMS5003 particulate matter sensors), when the territory of the Riga region is too large to create uniform coverage of the entire city, we focused on the city centre, where the building density is higher and the traffic higher, with low speeds and congestion leading to increased tailpipe aerosol emissions. As the Urban ReLeaf monitors are

specific to the measurement of PM_{2.5} particles that can be substantially affected by residential heating emissions in the winter (especially in cases where wood or other biomass products are burned), we also purposefully included in our network design neighbourhoods where individual heating devices are more common (as opposed to district heating that not generates point emissions at the residential buildings). Within the framework of the campaign, these sensors were adopted by various representatives: 3 Riga municipal institutions installed 7 sensors, 6 of which were installed in city parks, and one as a control sensor next to the official air quality monitoring station. Five sensors in total were adopted by state, municipal and private educational institutions in the city of Riga, installing sensors at their buildings, 2 at university buildings, one at the technical innovation centre, one at a secondary school and one at a kindergarten, another one was adopted by a non-governmental organisation, but the remaining 7 were handed over to residents who applied within the open call and whose places of residence and the technical compliance offered were the most appropriate for obtaining reliable data. An example of the installation process at one sensor site is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Installation process of AQ sensors in 2024.

As our focus was set on comparison of grey and green areas, as well as to additional data and provide public education, sensors were installed and still are gathering data in 4 types of sites: 2 sensors were installed in traffic (T) sites, 8 sensors at near-traffic (NT) sites, 5 sensors near urban green areas (NG) and 5 sensors with urban greenspaces (G). One of the near-green sensors was collocated with a reference monitor operating a regulatory site, for field validation purposes.

Technologies used during the campaigns

To monitor air quality levels and variability patterns in the Riga city centre, 20 PurpleAir PA-II air quality monitors were installed at 20 diverse sites, after in situ site characterization and preparation of a site characterization form, which ensures the quality of measurements and supports the analysis of the data. To recruit participants a survey was used to investigate the suitability of the applicant's sensor installation location for obtaining reliable data, as well as to learn more about the applicant's specifics and belonging to a certain population group. We track the status of fine aerosol pollution in Riga through the PurpleAir web site (<https://map.purpleair.com/>) and we also distributed information about the possibility of

monitoring the air quality indicators of the centre of Riga in real time to specialists and citizens of Riga. Calibrated data are also received in real-time through the Urban ReLeaf server maintained by projects partners at the National Observatory of Athens (NOA), and databases after quality assurance (QA) and quality control (QC) were periodically compiled in cooperation with NOA. An important and truly successful aspect is the excellent cooperation with Riga municipal authorities during both years of the campaign.

1.4 Citizen Engagement and Data Collection

Citizen participation in the campaign, the types of data collected

As there were mentioned before 7 sensors were handed over to residents who applied within the open call and whose places of residence and technical compliance were the most appropriate for obtaining reliable data. They installed sensors in their living or working places, they provide electricity and internet access for these sensors to operate, and they are following real-time data via the PurpleAir web site. Citizens as well provided some necessary information for site characterization forms to fill and gave clear answers about their sites' suitability for reliable data collection in the beginning of campaign. Some of volunteers that have submitted an application to participate in the Air Quality Campaign but were not selected to receive an AQ sensor, applied also for our second campaign, received TRH sensors and actively participated in temperature and humidity data gathering. Several learning events were organised within our second campaign as well as a final event for both campaigns, where all community members were invited to participate. The number of participants in the learning events and final event was smaller than expected, for reasons that are still under assessment.

Examples of data usage by local government, planners, other stakeholders

There have been several options considered to use data gathered within project. There was strong interest from our side to involve diverse educational institutions, expecting that data will be monitored and used by them, while also raising awareness about air quality in Riga. Lacking resources exclusive to the communication with educational institutions we had limited success in this direction so far, but we reached other results. A very important aspect is that representatives of the Riga City Council Housing and Environment Department are close partners in our project, and they are very interested in the opportunity to evaluate whether the operation of the sensors used in the project and the reliability of the data are of high quality. Accordingly, to assess whether the use of such low-cost solutions has the potential to be a provide data with sufficient quality to be reliable tool for air quality monitoring in the in the long term. Figure 4 features an image reproduced directly from the Riga City Air Quality Improvement Action Program for 2026–2030, the sensor network of the Urban ReLeaf project is explicitly presented, mentioning the data availability through a web platform, and the comparison with data by official monitoring at the national and city level. The text in the document specifically cites that: *“The results of this indicative monitoring for the period from March 2024 to March 2025 indicate trends that are consistent with the monitoring results of the LVGMC and RVP MVD, as well as the results of pollution dispersion.”* The results of the data analysed in the Action Plan show that the average values at 3 of the measurement sites correspond to the current limit value level, at the majority of sensor sites the average values are approximately halfway between the current limit value level and the level to be achieved in 2030, and at only a few sensor sites the average indicators correspond to the level to be achieved in 2030. We are still in the process of developing the data visualisation platform to provide historical data, that can be used in the future for assessing the impact of the Low emissions zone in Riga. We aim to develop this platform during 2026, as an additional key output of the Urban ReLeaf project.

Figure 4. Indicative PM2.5 sensor monitoring results from the Urban ReLeaf project (March 2024–March 2025), based on PurpleAir data (Source: Riga City Air Quality Improvement Action Program 2026–2030).

Results sharing with participants and communities

In both years of the campaign, online seminars were organised for all volunteers involved. In the first year the seminars introduced the project, the importance of air quality and the installation of sensors, and in the second year they presented the first results, discussed them and introduced the second campaign focused on heat stress and the possibilities of participation in it, as well. The results were also presented at the opening events of the second campaign and the closing event of both campaigns, although after the closing event the sensors continue to collect data and the volunteers are ready to ensure their operation as long as they are in working order and collecting data. In some cases, the campaign process and results were presented to the wider public through publicity materials including press releases, however, we hope to present the results more and more widely in the media in the final year of the project. An important aspect that should be mentioned here is that all collected data is made available to the municipality, more specifically, it can be accessed by specialists from

the Riga Digital Agency, while after data visualisation on the new platform, it will be available to a wide range of specialists and residents, with the opportunity to also view historical data for the entire data collection period at all sensor installation locations.

1.5 Findings and Reflections

Analysis of air quality data

The PM_{2.5} network has been operational at all sites since September 2024, providing near real-time measurements with high data coverage. The locations of these sites are displayed in Figure 5 below.

Figure 5. The installed PM_{2.5} sensor network, at 20 sites of different characterisation in Riga.

Results from the hourly concentration times series of 20 PurpleAir monitors were analysed for the first full year of measurements. The data are collected and processed by NOA on a weekly basis where the functioning of the sensors is also monitored. After a year of operation of the sensor network (September 2024 – August 2025), indicative results are provided for each type of location. Table 1 provides the relevant information on the location names as they are displayed online on the platform of the PurpleAir map (<https://map.purpleair.com>), as well as the completeness rates of the hourly and 24-hours' time series. For the hourly values, coverage was greater than 50% in all locations. The lowest data completeness was observed at the Miera (51%) and Brivibas (55%) sites, due to Wi-Fi transmission interruptions. For the valid daily averages, the coverage was greater than 70% at 17 sites.

Table 1. Information about AQ monitors and installation sites.

Device Name	Location Name	Site Type	Installation Date	Coverage* (hourly)	Coverage (valid 24-hours)**
URBAN_RELEAF_RIGA_01	RIGA_VIESTURDARZS	Urban Green	27/05/2024	99%	99%
URBAN_RELEAF_RIGA_02	RIGA_GRIZINKALNS	Urban Green	02/07/2024	99%	98%
URBAN_RELEAF_RIGA_04	RIGA_LU_JELGAVAS	Near Green	11/07/2024	87%	87%
URBAN_RELEAF_RIGA_05	RIGA_BRIVIBAS	Near Traffic	12/07/2024	55%	56%
URBAN_RELEAF_RIGA_06	RIGA_SLOKAS	Near Traffic	28/07/2024	98%	98%
URBAN_RELEAF_RIGA_07	RIGA_CAKA	Traffic	07/06/2024	97%	97%
URBAN_RELEAF_RIGA_08	RIGA_ANNAS	Near Traffic	22/05/2024	87%	87%
URBAN_RELEAF_RIGA_09	RIGA_PURVISA	Near Traffic	18/06/2024	98%	97%
URBAN_RELEAF_RIGA_10	RIGA_HOSPITALU	Near Green	29/06/2024	100%	99%
URBAN_RELEAF_RIGA_11	RIGA_HANZAS	Near Traffic	17/09/2024	71%	70%
URBAN_RELEAF_RIGA_12	RIGA_LU_RAINA	Near Green	17/07/2024	85%	85%
URBAN_RELEAF_RIGA_13	RIGA_ESPLANADE	Urban Green	27/05/2024	61%	62%
URBAN_RELEAF_RIGA_14	RIGA_GANIBU	Traffic	18/06/2024	94%	94%
URBAN_RELEAF_RIGA_15	RIGA_DARZAUGULU	Near Traffic	20/06/2024	99%	99%
URBAN_RELEAF_RIGA_16	RIGA_GRECINIEKU	Near Traffic	29/08/2024	84%	84%
URBAN_RELEAF_RIGA_17	RIGA_UZVARAS	Urban Green	22/05/2024	98%	96%
URBAN_RELEAF_RIGA_18	RIGA_MIERA	Urban Green	31/08/2024	51%	51%
URBAN_RELEAF_RIGA_19	RIGA_DZIRNAVU	Near Traffic	11/09/2024	90%	89%
URBAN_RELEAF_RIGA_20	RIGA_KONTROLSSENSORS	Near Green	06/08/2024	84%	84%
URBAN_RELEAF_RIGA_21	RIGA_ZIEDONDARZS	Near Green	29/05/2024	73%	73%

*The coverage rates refer to the period September 2024 – August 2025, when all instruments are in simultaneous operation.

**A 24-hour average concentration is considered valid when calculated from at least 18 (75%) valid hourly concentrations (EU) 2024/2881.

Descriptive statistics of the PM_{2.5} levels recorded at the network monitoring sites during the first year (September 2024 – August 2025) of operation are presented below (Table 2). To derive the results displayed on the table, the 24-hour average concentrations calculated from the field-calibrated hourly concentrations (with a completeness criterion of 18 valid values per 24-hour period) were used. Each monitor has its own calibration equation applied. Sensors were pre-calibrated at the NOA supersite at Thissio, Athens, and their performance in Riga

was validated through comparison to reference instruments at collocated and nearby monitoring sites. Data were processed for all monitors; however, 4 sites were excluded due to poor coverage, or unforeseen interferences from overly localized sources. The average annual concentration exceeded $10 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at 5 of the 16 measurement sites (the $10 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ is the updated EU annual limit values, so although its compliance should be assessed through reference monitors, the comparison with calibrated sensors can be indicative). The average concentration was lower, not only in urban green sites, but also at near-green locations, underpinning the importance of greenspaces and access to urban green for reducing the exposure of citizens. However, not all urban green locations followed the same pattern. A high value is observed at Uzvaras park, which seems to be influenced by nighttime emissions especially in the winter period, probably related to residential woodburning, since the monitors is located the site is located in the border of the park, close to residential areas in the eastern part of the city, where this type of heating is frequent.

According to EU Directive 2024/2881, the 24-hour limit value for $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ is set at $25 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, which should not be exceeded more than 18 times in a calendar year. Again, an indicative comparison is provided here, based on the data from the calibrated sensors. The results indicate that no site had such a large number of exceedances, although the traffic site of Caka was close (15 exceedances). An unexpectedly high number of days exceeding $25 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ was recorded at two non-traffic sites at the left bank of the Daugava river, indicating the need for source identification in this area. The results suggest that while there are should be no issues attaining the short-term air quality standard in the city of Riga, there might be pockets within the city (and maybe industrial and port areas outside the city core) where air quality is aggravated, due to local emissions (traffic, residential, medium/large combustion). This should be assessed by densifying the sensor network and utilizing the data for spatial and atmospheric modeling.

In addition to establishing a 24-hour limit value for $\text{PM}_{2.5}$, the new EU Directive, for the first time, foresees the monitoring of prolonged episodic concentrations of particulate matter, and stipulates alert and information thresholds for the protection of the population. For $\text{PM}_{2.5}$, the alert (and information) threshold is defined as a 24-hour average concentration above $50 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ exceeded for three consecutive days. During the measurement period, no violation of this threshold was observed.

Given that no severe exceedances of short-term thresholds were observed, the overall air quality in Riga was also assessed by means of a color-graduated Air Quality Index (AQI) as shown in Figure 6. The concentration intervals ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) for air quality characterization in relation to $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ proposed by the European Environment Agency (EEA) are: 0-10: Good, 10-20: Fair, 20-25: Moderate, 25-50: Poor, 50-75: Very Poor, >75: Extremely Poor. The following figure summarizes the air quality characterization results for Riga in relation to $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ levels, as assessed by applying the EEA air quality index to the 24-hour rolling average hourly concentrations. Based on the time series of hourly values of the 16 measurement sites, air quality was considered good or at least fair in 75-95% of the period at the majority of sites. Again, the traffic site of Caka stands out with the lower share of “good” air quality, and the largest percentage of “poor” air quality (4% of the time).

Table 2. Descriptive statistics on the concentrations recorded by the AQ sensor monitoring network (16/20 installed sites) during the first year of full operation (September 2024 – August 2025).

Location Name	Average annual \pm standard deviation	Maximum 24-hour average concentration	Number of days with 24-hour average concentration > 25 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$	Number of days with 24-hour average concentration > 10 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$
RIGA_VIESTURDARZS	8.7 \pm 4.9	35.5	6 (1.7%)	37 (10.2%)
RIGA_GRIZINKALNS	9.8 \pm 5.1	36.9	7 (1.9%)	51 (14.2%)
RIGA_LU_JELGAVAS	7.5 \pm 5.0	41.1	5 (1.6%)	20 (6.3%)
RIGA_SLOKAS	10.1 \pm 6.2	40.5	11 (3.1%)	53 (14.8%)
RIGA_CAKA	11.5 \pm 6.2	42.2	15 (4.2%)	75 (21.2%)
RIGA_ANNAS	9.7 \pm 5.8	40.9	9 (2.8%)	41 (13.0%)
RIGA_PURVISA	10.2 \pm 5.7	44.0	11 (3.1%)	54 (15.3%)
RIGA_HOSPITALU	9.0 \pm 5.5	38.6	6 (1.7%)	38 (10.5%)
RIGA_HANZAS	9. \pm 5.5	38.9	5 (2.0%)	35 (13.8%)
RIGA_LU_RAINA	8.3 \pm 5.5	39.2	5 (1.6%)	30 (9.6%)
RIGA_GANIBU	9.5 \pm 6.0	43.2	9 (2.6%)	46 (13.5%)
RIGA_DARZAUGULU	9.8 \pm 6.1	42.8	8 (2.2%)	53 (14.7%)
RIGA_GRECINIEKU	9.1 \pm 5.6	41.6	8 (2.6%)	32 (10.5%)
RIGA_UZVARAS	10.3 \pm 6.6	44.1	12 (3.4%)	63 (17.9%)
RIGA_DZIRNAVU	9.7 \pm 5.6	37.7	8 (2.5%)	49 (15.1%)
RIGA_KONTROLSORS	10.5 \pm 7.4	66.9	13 (4.2%)	46 (15.0%)

Figure 6. Distribution of PM_{2.5} concentrations in air quality categories for the annual measurement period in Riga. The assessment is based on calculated 24-hour rolling averages.

By examining the spatial variations of concentrations, it is evident that there were moderate mean traffic (T-NT, 8%) and urban (NT-UG, 7%) enhancements. Also, the benefits from vegetation buffering for near-green residential sites were clear. Urban green spaces were consistently linked to exposure reduction but were not fully isolated from transport or domestic emissions. The mean annual PM_{2.5} per site was inversely correlated with urban green space

area within a 1 km radius around sites as shown in the following Figure 7. This correlation ($r = -0.61$) was statistically significant, and it was verified that urban green and urban forested areas, can be important land-use predictors in spatial modeling, helping provide high resolution maps of $PM_{2.5}$ concentration over the entire Riga City region.

Figure 7. Mean annual $PM_{2.5}$ concentrations per site type correlated with the urban area in a radius of 1 km around each site.

The main findings from the first full year of AQ monitoring leveraging citizen science and sensor technologies in Riga can be summarized as follows:

- The first high-resolution AQ monitoring network in Riga showed clear spatiotemporal $PM_{2.5}$ contrasts.
- Urban greenspaces in Riga were consistently linked to exposure reduction, but do not fully isolate from transport/domestic emissions.
- The observed spatial contrasts underline the need to expand the regulatory AQ network in Riga, in view of the updated EU AQ directive, as annual-LV exceedances are probable at traffic locations and other pollution hotspots.
- The data from the calibrated LCS network can support AQ management and urban planning in the Region of Riga.
- The network's potential expansion can lead to efficient spatial modelling, exposure assessment, fusion with atmospheric models, and uptake by epidemiological studies.

Main outcomes of the campaigns

As a project team we have become much more educated in topics related to air quality and its significance, while seeing that citizens and representatives of institutions involved in project activities are more aware of air quality status in the city and seem interested in its improvement. We also believe that the City Council now has more options to develop data-driven solutions and to make decisions for the development of the city. Within the project and its campaigns, we managed to gather stakeholders that need to cooperate closely, exchanging information about their work, needs and opinions for better city governance.

Reflections

During the campaign, we repeatedly received clear confirmations that the interest of citizens in getting involved in data collection is much higher than we could have expected. It is often

not very successful communication, publications that did not reach the audience, or people's busy schedules create the perception that citizens are indifferent regarding the urban environment and well-being. The main key in our approach was our calls for involvement were convincing, visible through the most important communication channels and regular but not excessive or intrusive. Even after the official campaign ended, the adopters of all 20 sensors are still ready to ensure the continuous operation of the installed sensors. Representatives of involved institutions such as Riga Forests, Riga City Housing and Environment Department are following air quality data through the PurpleAir platform. Moreover, the representatives from the main Latvian institution responsible for collecting, storing and providing environmental information (LVGMC) to the public and institutions are following our project and have shown interest in the data gathered.

Lessons learned

Recruiting volunteers to adopt the sensors has been one of the most successful achievements of the campaign. We were pleasantly surprised by the high response rate right from the start, as a large proportion of the application forms were correctly completed, allowing us to fully assess the participants and the locations where they proposed to install the sensors, so as to select the most suitable sites. Moreover, the collaboration with Riga City institutions can be evaluated as very good. We received strong support to our ideas and activities from these institutions. Of course, there is still plenty of room for improvement in this cooperation, and much of it could be done on our side, if only the time and human resources were sufficient for the high-quality implementation of the numerous ideas put forward. We hope that we will be able to communicate more with volunteers from the AQ campaign in the final year of the project, so that they can be more often informed about the data they are providing and the analyses made based on their collected data. The feedback received from volunteers of AQ campaign indicates that they are happy to participate and support the operation of sensors, so that all Riga citizens can follow AQ data online and be informed about instances when AQ is reduced, therefore modifying the activities and reducing their exposure (e.g., by not going in outdoors in sporting activities, or by limiting open-window ventilation). Some volunteers did not participate in the educational events organised within second campaign as they were only interested in data gathering.

1.6 Recommendations and Future Steps

Efforts involved with Riga's Air Quality Campaign introduced specialists and citizens about volunteering in data gathering. As far as we know, previously these kinds of campaigns had not been implemented in Riga city. There is much higher interest to work with low-cost sensors in the city now and to involve citizens than before not only because of project but general tendencies where our experience encourages in these sensors' reliability and in citizen science as very good approach.

From our experience good lesson learned is about that citizens must be involved in sensors installation not only in several educational events and data following. We do not need to do all by ourselves if citizens and diverse institutions and organisations are interested and able to support us and better development of the city. With our open call approach and close collaboration with city we were able to install sensors in diverse locations in private and public spaces in the city centre. With this kind of approach city can continue similar activities in Riga city neighbourhoods to dive deeper into that context and citizens motivation.

It would likely be beneficial to have more than 20 AQ sensors for the scale of a such city as Riga to install sensors not only in city centre but also in other districts to have good coverage of the city environment and diverse citizen involvement. Clear and regular communication with volunteers about the process and results of data collection is very important to keep citizens close and motivated, and to feel awarded about their support in data collection.

2 Heat Stress Campaign

Campaign theme, approach, timeline, key events

When we started implementing the project, we thought and hoped that we would collect temperature and humidity readings, involving the public, similar to air quality monitoring, for two seasons, but we were only able to implement this initiative in 2025. In order to further emphasize the impact of climate change on our urban environment and the opportunities for each individual to change their habits and dedicate work and investments to the implementation of various nature-based solutions in the urban environment, we implemented the campaign "Take a step towards a greener city".

The Heat Stress Campaign was organised in three phases: preparation activities to reach audience and to plan organise events; active period focused on data collection, user consultations and educational events phase; conclusions and next steps focused on data analysis, results dissemination, discussion and conclusions.

The campaign was initially presented in 2024 to participants of the Air Quality Campaign. Since there was a higher interest to adopt air quality sensors in 2024 than the number of sensors available for installation, these interested community members were set as a priority for the assignment of TRH mobile sensors. During an online event information about heat islands and the impact of heat was presented, as well as an overview of the mobile sensors, EcoPulse App and web platform. Some members of the Air Quality Campaign community were interested to apply for participation in heat stress campaign, as well, and submitted their application to receive a mobile sensor.

When we started the campaign planning process, the project's scientific partners emphasized that community activities and the opportunity to socialize are among the most essential aspects of social science, so we started thinking early about inspirational events that would keep people engaged, renew their interest in going on new data collection missions, and make the entire data collection process more meaningful. At the campaign launch event (Figure 8), we aimed to gauge the range of interests of the participating residents by inviting them to vote on topics of interest, including giving them the opportunity to come up with their own questions of interest, as well as skills or stories they would like to share. The first community event we organised was the Campaign Launch event, to which we also invited participants from the first campaign. During this event, we identified topics of interest to the community and presented the initial results of the air quality campaign. We also introduced the TRH sensors, the EcoPulse app, the data platform, and the planned campaign activities. In addition, participants were invited to join the community WhatsApp group to receive up-to-date information, technical support, and a channel for reporting TRH sensor or EcoPulse app issues and asking questions.

Figure 8. Heat Stress Campaign Launch event, June 16th, 2025.

Within the active phase of the campaign, we organised 5 educational events, some of them more like dive-in tours in the city. One of the first educational events was a lecture on the greening plan currently being developed for Riga, as well as a scientist's story about studying heat islands using satellite data. We also went to the [Sports Palace Gardens](#) (Figure 9), which is the most popular urban gardening project in Riga, which hosts a strong community and is a vivid example of good practice in the temporary use of territories.

Figure 9. Guided tour in Sports Palace Gardens, July 16th, 2025.

We also arranged a video greeting from a professor at the University of Latvia who works with the popularization of social science. It was an excellent, refreshing and inspiring “push” to give energy to the community.

Members of the community were invited to participate in a walk through Riga’s green courtyards (Figure 10 and Figure 11), listening to stories from several storytellers who are lucky enough to live next to a green oasis--a landscaped courtyard. Each of these stories was unique in its own way and hopefully created a connection on a personal level with the participants, making them think about the functionality and potential of their own yard in both creating a better living environment and reducing the heat island effect.

Figure 10. A walk through the green courtyards, August 5th, 2025.

Figure 11. A walk through the green courtyards, August 5th, 2025.

It was a pleasure to show Riga's current sustainability issues by organising one of the cognitive events at "Sadarbnīca", a place dedicated to the circular economy, where people can create a more sustainable Riga together. There, under the guidance of an NGO named "Green Freedom" expert, we jointly understood the assessment of the donut economy in Riga, as well as discussed different sections of the donut and how we see it, whether we are in the donut safe zone or going beyond it.

The last cognitive activity was a walk along the "Green String" (Figure 12), which is an initiative to create a green pedestrian route through the courtyards of the Avoti neighbourhood connecting the blocks and creating a calmer alternative to the busy streets. It would serve as a green corridor for the city, allowing residents to get to Ziedoņdārzs, schools or service areas by walking along quieter, greener and safer paths. At the moment, it is difficult to imagine how the courtyards could be connected, because there are many barriers to be broken down, both physical (in the form of fences and walls) and mental. We thought about whether we, as the owners of the specific courtyards, would like to open the courtyards to all Riga residents? Or would we trade security for a more pleasant outdoor space?

Figure 12. A walk along the "Green String", September 15th, 2025.

During autumn 2025 we brought together volunteers from both of our campaigns and held an official closing event for both campaigns. During this event, a representative from the Latvian Centre for Environment, Geology and Meteorology presented climate change observations in Latvia over the past 100 years and future projections. The project team also shared the results of data analysis from both campaigns so far, and commemorated the most active, enthusiastic and supportive data collection participants in the heat island mapping campaign. In the conclusion of event there was a session of reflection which also included three brief lectures and important feedback from community members.

2.1 Context and Objectives

Local challenges the campaign addressed

The impact of climate change also directly affects the city of Riga. Phenomena such as heat waves, torrential rains, and rapidly changing weather conditions are felt much more intensely in Riga, as in other large cities, than in areas closer to the natural environment. Heat islands can be observed in more and more parts of the city, as evidenced by the results of satellite data on surface temperatures analysed by researchers over several years. The urban heat island effect and its impact on the health of residents, infrastructure, and the quality of the urban environment are in the focus of specialists involved in the industry, as well as municipal specialists and political representatives already for many years.

Connection to local, regional, national and EU priorities

Climate neutrality is one of the highest priorities at all levels of governance and many important policy documents have been developed to achieve it. Similarly, the health and well-being of citizens in cities, resource adequacy and ensuring environmental quality are in the focus of the European Union and its urban policies, as well as in Riga. By regularly collecting data that reflects the parameters characterizing the quality of the urban environment, we can continually evaluate and review the effectiveness of existing policies and actions taken, plan and make new data-based decisions and determine new, data-based actions. On city level as a main strategic planning documents are Riga Sustainable Development Strategy 2030 and Riga Development Program for 2022–2027--both setting environmental quality and citizens wellbeing as very high priorities. To implement more exact actions there are developed or in development process thematic policy documents like Riga Greening plan, Low emission zone, Air quality action program.

The overarching objectives of the campaign

In general, we focused on promoting awareness of heat islands in urban environment and the role of green areas in relation to them. We also aimed to inform about AQ sensors and raise awareness about the correlation between heat and air quality deterioration in places that are excessively hot, where there is a lack of vegetation. Our main goal set was to involve diverse groups of society in data gathering and to take a part in discussions about results that data gathered are showing in addition to what we can do for situation to be improved.

In both campaigns, the focus is on the high density of cars in the city centre and how much public outdoor space they occupy. The aim is to assess this impact and to support the creation of a greener, more liveable environment for residents of Riga's city centre. Riga City is currently developing a Greening Plan, which is scheduled for completion in summer 2026 and is part of the LIFE LATESTadapt project. Both LIFE LATESTadapt and the SATSDIFACTION project have targeted outcomes will include a heat island layer derived from satellite data. The Riga pilot Urban ReLeaf team is working in close collaboration with both projects to exchange knowledge and align methodologies for mapping heat islands, as well as to explore how the projects can complement each other.

2.2 Design and Implementation

Overall design of the campaign

In order to further emphasize the impact of climate change on our urban environment and the opportunities for each individual to change their habits and dedicate work and investments to the implementation of various nature-based solutions in the urban environment, we implemented the campaign "Take a step towards a greener city". We divided this campaign in three phases: preparation activities to reach audience and to plan organise events; active period focused on data collection, user consultations and educational events phase;

conclusions and next steps focused on data analysis, results dissemination, discussion and conclusions.

When we started the campaign planning process, the project's scientific partners emphasized that community activities and the opportunity to socialize are among the most essential aspects of social science, so we started thinking early about inspirational events that would keep people engaged, renew their interest in going on new data collection missions, and give the entire data collection process more meaning.

Key partners and stakeholders involved

We identified five main audience groups to reach general and potentially vulnerable populations for participation in the TRH sensor campaign:

1. Active Citizens (Early Adopters)
 - Citizens who had previously signed up for air quality sensors (including those on waiting lists) and those already participating but interested in TRH sensors.
 - Prioritized due to their high motivation and potential for continued collaboration.
 - Allocated sensors: ~20.
2. Neighbourhood Association Activists
 - Members of neighbourhood associations in six central Riga neighbourhoods (Avoti, Brasa, Centrs, Grīziņkalns, Pētersala–Andrejsala, Skanste).
 - Five sensors were planned per association.
 - Allocated sensors: ~30.
3. General Public (Open Call)
 - Residents applying through an open call promoted via press releases and QR-code information signs in public spaces.
 - Intended to reach a broad and diverse audience beyond organized groups.
 - Allocated sensors: ~20.
4. Vulnerable and Occupational Groups
 - Planned distribution to central park gardeners (via Riga Forests) and Riga traffic control workers to reach groups with higher environmental exposure.
 - This collaboration was only partially implemented due to organizational responsibility concerns.
 - Planned allocation: ~20.
5. City and Regional Specialists
 - Professionals from Riga city institutions and regional planning bodies.
 - Allocated sensors: ~10.

The open call proved to be the most successful channel, attracting a highly diverse group of participants, including residents of different ages, institutional representatives, students, neighbourhood activists, parents of newborns, and regular city-centre walkers (e.g. dog owners).

Strategies used to engage diverse target groups

The key success to reach quite large number of applicants was our open call to participate in mapping of heat islands, which was widely advertised in the media, national television, radio, print media and websites. We received 76 applications within open call published and invited to participate specialists from Riga Planning region and Riga City Council development department, as well. We did not succeed with involvement of gardeners of central parks via Riga Forests and Riga traffic company workers, who are walking through the streets and checking the parking tickets, as well as with involvement of neighbourhood associations, but we are happy that diversity of community members is high and in general we are that satisfied with our citizen engagement results.

2.3 Areas of Focus and Technologies Used

Geographic areas, neighbourhoods where the campaign was implemented

We kept the same area for both campaigns, so we were focusing on city centre including the primary Riga historic centre (438 ha) and protected urban areas (1574 ha) located in the neighbourhoods shown in Figure 13. Focus was placed on including participants that live or work in or near the city centre and walk regularly and on diverse routes, as well as we were interested that diverse age groups are presented, that participants are spending their summer in Riga and are not away to long time during the summer vacations.

Figure 13. Map of Riga city neighbourhoods.

Technologies used during the campaign

To implement our heat stress campaign three main technologies were used: TRH sensors, the mobile app Eco Pulse and publicly available website: <https://platform-urbanreleaf.iccs.gr/>. Sensors were used to collect temperature and relative humidity data mainly in Riga city centre by citizens' regular walks and diverse walks to give an opportunity to compare situation in parks, in streets with and without greenery. The mobile app gives users the opportunity to monitor their walking routes and understand when the heat affects them the most. We also used mobile app WhatsApp to communicate with participants directly about technical problems, their experience and challenges, and used this channel also to invite to educational events. We shared a feedback questionnaire twice including once in the midterm and in the end of campaign. From this communication with participants and face-to-face conversations we know that all participants were interested to use app in Riga to monitor their walks even if data collection goes on also without missions recording. If the EcoPulse app works well and users have a chance to monitor their walks, they are motivated and only then they truly believe that sensors are collecting data properly. We also built trust with participants through the extensive technical advice we shared, as technical partners provided us clarifications and helpful was also website, where users can see data received from sensors they wear. The only challenge with that was the time, because of data transferring too slowly, at least couple of weeks users needed to wait until data were visible on website.

2.4 Citizen Engagement and Data Collection

Citizen participation in the campaign, types of data collected

Announcing the open application, inviting residents to participate in the collection of temperature and relative humidity data, we carried out extensive publicity on the main social networks, national television, radio and various digital and print media. In this way, we received a high response and interest in participating in the campaign. A total of 75 applications were sent to us and from the completed questionnaires we could conclude that most applicants are highly motivated and want such data to be collected and analysed, moving the city forward and for good changes.

In the first month of the campaign, we managed to gather a third of the applicants while the remaining two thirds of those who applied for participation we met sequentially over several weeks to hand over the sensor and train in its use, and in the operation of the EcoPulse app. In parallel with the process of distributing the sensors, we began active work on planning and organising educational events. We hoped for a higher response from the participants in these events, perhaps because many participants often had their evenings already occupied with other activities or daily worries, so the attendance at various events ranged from 8 to 15 participants.

Important and valuable community activities took place in the community WhatsApp group. Specified sections have been created for this community group: announcements, service, observations and a third space for events. In this community group, participants actively reported technical problems, tried to understand the problems and offered their own experiences, what connections they had noticed, what works better, while we tried to provide answers to all questions received, by involvement of project's technical partners and excerpts from instructions. The community group was also a good platform for reminding about news and current events.

Examples of data usage by local government, planners, other stakeholders

During the initial months of project implementation, we identified the key planning documents for urban development in Riga, including the Riga Sustainable Development Strategy (until 2030), the Development Program 2022–2027, and thematic documents addressing climate change challenges, such as the Riga City Air Quality Improvement Action Program and the

Riga City Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan. In both of our campaigns, we have actively engaged relevant stakeholders to collaboratively define our needs and advance the development of a data visualization platform. This platform will soon allow specialists and citizens to explore city data collected from a variety of sensors. It will initially feature data from the sensors deployed in the Urban ReLeaf project, as well as data from all other sensors currently available to the city, specifically for integration by the Riga Digital Agency into the new platform. We hope that new platform will ensure that data collected in both campaigns will be used when the city will monitor planning documents and develop new documents, in which conclusions will be drawn based on the analysed data, and actions will be planned to improve the quality of the urban environment.

We had also identified thematically similar projects that are with similar implementation period as Urban ReLeaf project and involved the implementers of these projects in the first design event of both campaigns in the beginning of project in 2023. Close collaboration developed with two projects: Interreg Europe project SATSDIFACTION and LIFE project LIFE LATESTadapt. During both campaigns we have followed activities of these projects and representatives of these projects have followed ours, as well as some of representatives wears TRH sensors in their walks in city centre. We were invited from both projects to share results from our AQ and Heat Stress Campaigns (Figure 14 and Figure 15). Within events we exchanged knowledge gained from experience gained in our projects, we discussed strong and weak sides from diverse methods of data collection and analyse, we also agreed on that such data like satellite and sensor data best could work better analysed in combination.

Figure 14. Presentation in SATDISFACTION event.

Results sharing with participants and communities

At the start of the campaign, we organized two events: an online event for volunteers who had adopted sensors or submitted forms to adopt one, and a live opening event for the Heat Stress Campaign. During the online event, we presented the results of our first Air Quality Campaign and introduced participants to the opportunity to join this year's second heat stress campaign. The results from the first-year AQ campaign were also shared at the live opening event. Throughout the campaign activities, participants had the chance to attend educational events, where we shared key information and main conclusions derived from our web platform data. We also provided participants with the number of measurements collected by each sensor

during these events. While midterm messages or press releases could have improved communication, we were not able to implement them at the time.

Figure 15. Presentation in LIFE LATESTadapt event.

2.5 Findings and Reflections

Participation and data coverage

The Riga Heat Stress Campaign achieved broad spatial and temporal coverage across the summer period from June to September 2025. Data were collected from 54 devices, resulting in a total of 49,264 paired temperature and relative humidity observations within a 50 km radius of the city centre (Figure 16 shows the spatial coverage of these observations). Of these, 47,816 observations fall within the core spatial extent used for most analyses.

Data collection occurred between June and September 2025, with days containing data recording an average of approximately 573 measurements. The number of observations per device varied substantially, ranging from 22 to nearly 9,000 records. Figure 17 shows the amount of data collected by each device, ranked from highest to lowest. This reflects a common participation pattern in citizen-driven sensing campaigns, where a relatively small subset of highly active participants contributes a large share of the data.

Spatially, observations cluster along frequently travelled routes and residential areas, with notable overlap in high-activity zones. A spatial density analysis using 100 × 100 m grid cells highlights uneven coverage across the city, reflecting differences in individual mobility patterns and daily routines.

Figure 16. Spatial coverage of sensor measurements in Riga on a log scale.

Figure 17. Amount of data by device. (Counting a pair of relative humidity and temperature as one observation and ignoring the button records).

Measurements in Riga are distributed across the full day, including afternoon, evening, and nighttime periods. Figure 18 displays all temperature measurements collected in summer, overlaid over the same 24-hour cycle. This temporal spread enables analysis of diurnal temperature dynamics and provides coverage during periods that are particularly relevant for understanding urban heat retention and nighttime cooling behaviour.

Figure 18. All temperature measurements throughout the days, with the median line and the 25 and 75 quartiles for each hour shown.

Temperature findings

Recorded temperatures range from 9.6 °C to 40.2 °C, capturing a wide spectrum of summer thermal conditions. Mobile sensor measurements are consistently higher than those recorded at nearby meteorological reference stations. On average, mobile sensors measured temperatures 4.39 °C higher than reference values. This difference varies throughout the day, with the largest deviations occurring during evening and nighttime hours and smaller differences observed around the afternoon temperature peak. These dynamics are consistent with established urban heat island processes, where built environments retain heat and limit nocturnal cooling.

Data quality and challenges

GPS accuracy varies across the dataset. A recurring pattern involves erratic positioning at the beginning or end of trips, likely due to poor satellite reception indoors or delayed GPS lock-on. These artefacts can result in implausible jumps or speeds inconsistent with typical pedestrian movement, as seen in the example of Figure 19 below, and require filtering or correction prior to detailed spatial analyses.

Figure 19. Example of a trip with dubious GPS records based on erratic measurements at the end of a trip, with speed in km/h.

Temperature measurement limitations

The mobile sensors lack standardized radiation shielding, making temperature measurements susceptible to solar heating of the sensor casing. Sensor placement, user behaviour, and environmental context introduce unobserved variability, contributing to systematic measurement bias. The observed offset relative to reference stations likely reflects a combination of genuine street-level microclimatic conditions and sensor-related effects.

Methodological considerations

The unstructured nature of mobile, citizen-generated sensor data differs from traditional fixed-station or controlled transect approaches. Observations are collected along semi-random paths, at varying times, and under heterogeneous conditions. While this increases analytical complexity, the dataset remains valuable for characterising street-level thermal environments when supported by careful cleaning and modelling.

Next steps

With appropriate quality control and contextualisation, the Riga dataset can support urban microclimate modelling, comparative cross-city analyses, and studies of heat exposure and thermal comfort. Future deployments would benefit from improved sensor shielding, clearer participant guidance, and mechanisms allowing users to flag questionable data to further enhance data quality.

Main outcomes of the campaign

As a project team we were in a pretty good level of knowledge about climate changes and urban heat islands, as well as about significance of greenery for better quality of urban environment, but we are glad within campaign to get more knowledges and updates in this field and now we are much more experienced in citizens science use in science and practise,

and we are more aware of citizens' general understanding about heat stress and options for improvements. We also believe that City Council has more options to develop data-based solutions and to make data-based decisions for city development. Within project and its campaign, we managed to gather stakeholders that need to work closely to present each other their work, needs and opinions for better performance of city governance.

Reflections

During the campaign, we consistently received strong confirmation that citizens' interest in participating in data collection was much higher than we had anticipated. Although ineffective communication, publications that fail to reach the audience, or people's busy schedules can create a perception of societal indifference, the real determining factor is whether our calls for participation are convincing, visible on key channels, and consistent--without being excessive or intrusive.

Even after the official campaign ended, fewer than a quarter of participants (16 out of 62) decided to return their sensors as initially planned and indicated that they wanted to continue collecting TRH data with the sensors. Nevertheless, all participants expressed interest in continuing to collect data if the opportunity remained available. Some communicated that they would be interested in collecting data with a different sensor due to technical issues.

Lessons learned and feedback from participants

As previously mentioned, the way the open call was published worked very well and resulted in a high response rate from the very beginning. A large share of the application forms were completed with good quality, which allowed us to assess participants' motivation to walk with the sensor and to collect data in a reliable way. This confirms that clear communication and transparency are especially important in citizen science campaigns that involve sensors, mobile applications, or web platforms. Such technologies need to perform at least well, even if they are still being tested, in order to keep participants motivated and to maintain their trust that the data they collect will be used responsibly and meaningfully for improving urban environments and citizens' wellbeing.

At the end of the Heat Stress Campaign, a feedback questionnaire was shared with participants, and 16 responses were received. Regarding the participant profile, 62.5% of respondents were male and 37.5% female. Participants were between 18 and 64 years old, with the largest age group being 35–44 years. Most participants were highly educated, with nearly 70% holding a master's degree, and almost all were employed full time. Most of them lived or worked in the city centre. When asked about their living conditions during summer heat, participants gave diverse answers, ranging from homes that stay relatively cool to dwellings that become uncomfortably hot during heat waves. These varied experiences provided a useful context for reflecting on heat stress during the campaign.

Participant activity levels during the campaign also varied. About one-third of respondents reported using the sensor every day or almost every day, and a similar share reported using it twice a week, while around one-fifth used it rarely. Several participants noted that they were more active at the beginning of the campaign but became less active later on due to technical disturbances. When reflecting on their experience with the sensor, only two participants reported that they had not encountered any problems. Most comments referred to issues related not so much to the sensor itself but to the mobile application and its interaction with the sensor.

The evaluation of the EcoPulse app clearly shows that this was a weaker element of the campaign from the participants' perspective. App ratings were significantly lower than those for the sensor, with most participants rating the app with 1 or 2 on a five-point scale and no participant giving the highest rating of 5 (Figure 20). Participants reported frequent problems such as interrupted missions, long data upload times, missions not being saved, difficulties

with GPS location, and uncertainty about whether data were being collected at all if no mission was visible in the app. Many participants emphasised that missions could only be recorded reliably when the app was kept open, even though background operation permissions were enabled. These issues reduced confidence in the technology and, for some, reduced motivation to continue walking with the sensor.

Figure 20. Participant ratings of the EcoPulse app (1-5 scale).

Figure 21. Participants' indication of willingness to participate in future Heat Stress Campaign activities.

When asked how often they encountered technical problems, half of the participants reported experiencing them often or very often. Almost all participants noted long data upload processes and missions not being saved, while more than half reported problems with location accuracy and interruptions during missions. About half also encountered sudden app closures, partially saved missions, or missing temperature and humidity data. Technical problems had a clear impact on motivation: half of the participants stated that these issues demotivated them, although some continued thanks to technical support or personal interest in testing new technologies. At the same time, the importance of support became very clear. The WhatsApp chat was almost unanimously mentioned as a very helpful and motivating support channel, helping participants solve problems, share experiences, and maintain a sense of community.

Despite the technical challenges, participants evaluated the overall value of the campaign very positively. Almost all agreed that the collected data are useful for urban planning and that the campaign helped them better understand the heat island effect and its connection to health. Many participants reported a stronger sense of belonging to the community involved in the project and greater appreciation of trees, shade, and greenery as key elements for cooling the city. Willingness to continue participation in the future remained high: around two-thirds of participants stated that they would continue collecting data next summer, while about one-fifth would do so if technical improvements are made (Figure 21). This shows that, while technical reliability remains a key challenge, the motivation of participants and the perceived relevance of the campaign provide a strong basis for future improvements and continued engagement.

2.6 Recommendations and Future Steps

We will continue to cooperate with thematically related projects with which we already cooperate and will also cooperate with other, new ones, if any will be developed or implementation will be started to exchange experiences, data and results. We will continue to actively support the community and project stakeholders with interesting news, data analysis results, new engagement opportunities, technical support and small competitions. We will involve the community in the implementation of the Pop-up culture Lab project in Riga, where we plan to create a mural on nine railway bridge pillars, next to the central station, taking care of a remote and not very welcoming place for citizens and its visitors, making it more attractive and substantively speaking about important topics for the city and its citizens, which we are looking at in the Urban ReLeaf project. We will continue to work and reach results in the creation of a data visualisation platform, in cooperation with the Riga Digital Agency, ensuring the availability of data from all sensors installed in the city or used in city to be available to researchers, specialists and residents. We will inform the city's responsible specialists and politicians about the project results and the possibilities of using them in the planning and practical implementation of future development processes.

We noticed during the heat stress campaign that all technologizes we plan to use for citizen science needs to be in very high readiness to use, to be user friendly, convenient, simple and attractive for diverse target groups so we can much more involve vulnerable groups and they could be opened to participate, so we can involve non-active citizens and make them more opened for volunteering and science, and data based arguments instead of populism and conspiracy theories.

That what we have done in Riga city can done almost all dense cities not so much for data collection and data analyse but for citizens engagement and educational activities – for citizens and with citizens to understand better environmental challenges and options for us to improve our habits.

Appendices

Appendix A: Open call for campaign “Adopt a sensor”

The screenshot shows a news article on the Urban ReLeaf website. The header includes the Urban ReLeaf logo, a navigation menu with links for Home, Project, Cities, Resources, News, and Get involved, and a 'News' button. The article title is 'Riga Planning Region Launches 'Adopt a Sensor' Campaign', dated 14th March 2024, with a 2-minute read time. A large image of Riga, Latvia, is featured below the title. The article text describes the campaign's goal to engage residents in air quality measurements and provides background on PM2.5 pollution in Latvia.

Urban ReLeaf

Home Project Cities Resources News Get involved

[← Back to all articles](#)

News

Riga Planning Region Launches 'Adopt a Sensor' Campaign

2 min read • 14th March 2024

The Riga Planning Region calls on local residents to engage in air quality measurements in Riga. This Urban ReLeaf campaign aims to facilitate evidence-based urban planning, aligning with the European Green Deal and Sustainable Development Goals.

Using sensors, the campaign seeks to gather data on air quality, temperature, and variability across different areas of Riga City Centre.

PM2.5 pollution is a significant environmental hazard, causing premature mortality. In the European Union in 2018, 380,000 deaths were attributed to PM2.5 and 75,000 to Nitrogen Dioxide and Ozone combined. The ratio is even more pronounced in Latvia with 1,800 deaths attributed to PM2.5 pollution compared to 130 from NO₂ and O₃.

Only two official monitoring stations in Riga measure PM2.5, the city has a need for additional data to support better decision-making. Therefore, from May 2024 to April 2026, 20 air quality sensors will be placed throughout the city, with a focus on PM2.5 pollution.

The study aims to educate stakeholders and compare air quality between urban green spaces and high-traffic areas. Seven sensors will be placed in green areas, while thirteen will be installed in collaboration with residents across various locations in the City Centre.

This opportunity is ideal for individuals interested in Riga's air quality, or who are keen to learn about citizen science and those residing in or near the city centre. Participation involves filling out an application form, with thirteen residents being selected based on the suitability of proposed sensor locations and project requirements.

Project Funders

Urban ReLeaf has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No.101086638. UK participants in the Urban ReLeaf project are supported by United Kingdom Research and Innovation ("UKRI") Innovate UK under grant agreements 10061290 and 10041792.

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Project Partners

Home
Project
Cities

Resources
News & stories
Get involved

Contact
hello@urbanreleaf.eu

Co-ordination
Inian Moorthy and Gerid Hager
IIASA

Appendix B: Application form to fill in to adopt an AQ sensor

1. sadaļa no 2

Anketa par pieteikšanos adoptēt PM 2.5 sensoru

Rīgas plānošanas reģions projekta "Urban ReLeaf – Iedzīvotāju virzītas datu ekosistēmas pārejai uz iekļaujošu un zaļu pilsētvidi" ietvaros aicina iedzīvotājus piedalīties gaisa kvalitātes mērījumu veikšanā Rīgas pilsētā. Aicinām aizpildīt aptauju, kas palīdzēs izprast, vai esi piemērots sensora "adoptēšanai".

Pētījumā tiks izvēlēti 13 iedzīvotāji, prioritāti dodot tiem, kuru piedāvātā sensoru izvietojuma vieta vislabāk atbilst vietās mikro un makro nosacījumiem, kā arī projekta specifikai.

Informācija par personas datu apstrādi saistībā ar anketu:

Apstrādes nolūki, kam paredzēti personas dati, apstrādes tiesiskais pamats un ilgums:

Jūsu personas datu apstrādes nolūks ir saziņa par Jūsu turpmāk anketā norādīto iesaistes veidu projektā. Tiesiskais pamats – Jūsu sniegta piekrišana, atbilstoši Vispārīgās datu aizsardzības regulas 6.panta 1.punkta a) apakšpunktam, kas sniegta brīvi, konkrēti un apzināti. Apstrādes ilgums - līdz piekrišanas atsaukšanai vai līdz pētījuma izstrādes beigām.

Informējam, ka Jūs jebkurā brīdī variet atsaukt savu piekrišanu datu apstrādei, rakstot uz e-pastu: nora.gagane@riga.lv

Informējam, ka Jūs atbildiet par pareizu un precīzu savu datu iesniegšanu, kā arī informējam, ka trešo personu datu iesniegšana nav pieļaujama un var tikt uzskatīta par tiesību aktu pārkāpumu.

Personas datu saņēmēji:

Dalībnieku personas datus apstrādās Rīgas plānošanas reģiona projekta "Urban Releaf" darbinieki.

Kāds ir Jūsu vārds, uzvārds? *

Īsās atbildes teksts

Kāds ir Jūsu telefona numurs? *

Īsās atbildes teksts

Vai vēlaties norādīt kā savu epastu to, caur kuru pašlaik pildat aptauju? Ja nē, lūgums precizēt *
vēlamo epastu saziņai.

Jā

Citas:

Kādā adresē Jūs plānojat novietot sensoru? *

Īsās atbildes teksts

AWAITING VALIDATION
EUROPEAN COMMISSION

Lai mēs izprastu, kurai no tematiskajām sensora vietām vislabāk atbilst Jūsu piedāvātā sensora atrašanās vieta, lūdzam atzīmēt laukus, kas ir atbilstoši! (makro nosacījumi) *

MAKRO NOSACĪJUMI SENSORU NOVIETOJUMAM

- ✓ **SATIKSMEŠ** – parāda transportlīdzekļu radīto emisiju ietekmi

Sensors atrodas 2 līdz 10 m no intensīvas satiksmes ceļa (>10 000 transportlīdzekļu dienā),
Parauga ņemšanas augstums vēlams <4 m, atjaus <7 m
- ✓ **PILSĒTAS FONĀ** – atspoguļo dzīves vidi lielākajai daļai iedzīvotāju

Vietām jābūt > 50 m attālumā no intensīvas satiksmes ceļiem.
Paraugu ņemšanas augstums nav ierobežojošs (ir pieļaujams līdz 15 m).
Projekta specifikas dēļ sadalām divās apakšgrupās – TUVUMĀ SATIKSMEI un TUVUMĀ ZAĻAJAI TELPAI
Attālums līdz luskoforiem, autobusa pieturām un krustojumiem > 25 m
- ✓ **ZAĻĀS ZONAS** – atspoguļo gaisa kvalitāti pilsētas parkos

Sensori tiks izvietoti pilsētas parkos un zaļajās zonās (par šo parūpēsities mēs)

- Sensors tiks novietots augstumā no 2 līdz 7 metriem (1.; 2. stāvs)
- Sensors tiks novietots augstumā no 7 līdz 15 metriem (2.;3. stāvs)
- Sensors atradīsies 2 līdz 10 m no intensīvas satiksmes ceļa (tiešā tuvumā)
- Sensors atradīsies tālāk par 50 m no intensīvas satiksmes ceļiem
- Sensors atradīsies tuvumā zaļajām zonām (tuvumā (līdz 50 m) ir liels parks/ mežs / vērā ņemama zaļā z...)
- Sensora attālums līdz luskoforiem, autobusa pieturām un krustojumiem būs lielāks par 25 m
- Citas:

AM...
EU...

Kur Jūs plānojat novietot sensoru? (mikro nosacījumi) *

- Uz balkona
- Uz palodzes
- Uz jumta
- Pagalmā
- Piestiprināt pie staba
- Citas:

Vai Jūsu plānotā sensora uzstādīšanas vieta atbilst novietojuma mikro nosacījumiem?

MIKRO NOSACĪJUMI SENSORU NOVIETOJUMAM

- ✓ ELEKTRĪBAS un PRIVĀTA WI-FI pieejamība ir galvenās prasības
- ✓ WI-FI signālam jābūt nepārtrauktam un pēc iespējams labākam
- ✓ Ierīcei jāatrodas 1,5 m virs virsmas (nevis no zemes, bet no, piemēram, balkona grīdas)
- ✓ Vēlams atrasties atstatus no sienām (> 1m), lai netiktu pārtraukta brīvā plūsma un netiktu uztvertas daļiņas, kas atsītas pret sienu.
- ✓ Jābūt brīvai telpai 270° ap ierīci. Priekšroka tiek dota atklātām telpām, jāizvairās no slēgtām telpām (piemēram, ātrijiem, slēgtiem balkoniem).

- Izvēlētajā vietā ir/būs pieejama elektrība
- Izvēlētajā vietā ir pieejams pietiekams wifi signāls
- Ierīce atradīsies 1,5 m virs virsmas (nevis no zemes, bet no, piemēram, balkona grīdas)
- Senors tiks novietots atstatus no sienām (> 1m)
- Tiks nodrošināta brīva telpa 270 grādu platumā ap ierīci
- Citas:

Vai varēstiet pats/i nodrošināt sensora piestiprināšanu pie sienas/ metāla staba /palodzes, vai būs nepieciešams tehniskais cilvēks, kas varēs aiziet uz dzīvokli un sensoru piestiprināt? *

- Varēšu sensoru uzstādīt pats
- Domāju, ka varēšu sensoru uzstādīt pats, bet noderētu ieteikumi/ pamācība, kā to darīt
- Man būs nepieciešama palīdzība
- Citas:

Ja sensoram būs jāveic apkope, vai nepieciešamības gadījumā varēsiet nodrošināt speciālistam pieeju sensoram? *

- Jā, iepriekš vienojoties par laiku
- Citas:

Kāda ir Jūsu motivācija piedalīties aktivitātē? *

Garās atbildes teksts

.....

Vai piekrītat iesaistīties pētījumā 2 gadus? *

- Jā
- Citas:

Vai piekrītat parakstīt līgumu un pieņemšanas - nodošanas aktu par sensora saņemšanu un uzstādīšanu? *

- Jā
- Citas:

Neatkarīgi no tā, vai Jūsu piedāvātā sensora vieta tiek apstiprināta, labprāt iepazītos un/vai dalītos tālāk ar projektā gūto informāciju. *

- Jā, esmu ieinteresēts saņemt aktuālo informāciju par projekta aktivitātēm Rīgas pilsētā
- Nē, neesmu ieinteresēts saņemt aktuālo informāciju par projekta aktivitātēm Rīgas pilsētā
- Citas:

AWAITING VALIDATION BY THE
EUROPEAN COMMISSION

Appendix C: Adopt a Sensor' Success: Riga Engages Citizens in Air Quality Monitoring

Urban ReLeaf

Home Project Cities Resources News Get involved

[← Back to all articles](#)

News

'Adopt a Sensor' Success: Riga Engages Citizens in Air Quality Monitoring

4 min read · 26th September 2024

We are excited to announce a significant milestone in Riga's urban air quality initiative: the successful installation of 20 air quality sensors across the city, marking the completion of the project's first phase. This achievement brings us one step closer to creating data-driven, sustainable urban design solutions that align with the European Green Deal and Sustainable Development Goals.

Earlier this year, we launched the 'Adopt a Sensor' campaign, inviting Riga's residents to take an active role in this initiative by hosting air quality sensors in their homes or workplaces. Thanks to the enthusiastic response, we were able to identify key participants and, together with the community, strategically place these sensors throughout different neighbourhoods. For this pilot phase, our focus has been on the city centre and surrounding areas, allowing us to capture a diverse range of data.

In collaboration with SIA 'Rīgas meži', five of these sensors have been placed in city parks, while the remaining 15 were installed in various high-traffic and green areas. We're especially proud to have engaged a wide cross-section of the community – participants include residents from central Riga as well as institutions like the University of Latvia, the Technical Creativity Center '2 Annas', Riga State Gymnasium No. 3, and Montessori Kindergarten 'Krāsainas pērles'. Together, these sensors will provide crucial insights, especially regarding PM2.5 pollution, one of the most harmful pollutants to human health.

Previously, certified PM2.5 sensors were limited to just two locations in Riga: one near the National Theater in the city center and another in Bierīni near Akmens Garden. With this expansion, we are greatly enhancing the city's air quality monitoring network. Perhaps one of these sensors have been installed near your residence. To explore the real-time air quality data map please [click here](#).

In the coming months, we'll begin analysing the data collected from these sensors and share the first results with the public. We hope this project will spark a greater understanding of air quality issues and inspire ongoing efforts to enhance our urban environment.

PM2.5 pollution poses a significant risk to human health, yet we know surprisingly little about it. It's invisible to the naked eye, but ever-present in the air around us. Through this project, we aim to deepen our collective understanding of its sources and how it fluctuates across the city. Thank you to everyone who has shown interest and participated in the project!

To find out more information please visit: [Riga Planning Region](#)

AWAITING V
EUROPEAN

Appendix D: Press release and posters: Open call to become a researcher of heat islands

The screenshot shows a website page with a dark green header. The Urban ReLeaf logo is in the top left. A navigation menu in the top right includes 'Home', 'Project', 'Cities', 'Resources', 'News', and 'Get involved'. Below the header, there is a link '← Back to all articles' and a 'News' button. The main title of the article is 'Help Shape a Greener Riga: Join the Urban ReLeaf Citizen Science Project', with a sub-headline '2 min read • 23rd May 2025'. Below the title is a photograph of a man and a woman walking a dog on a paved path through a lush green park. The text below the photo reads: 'Riga gets hot in the summer, especially in the city centre, where there are fewer trees and buildings trap heat. Can you help change that?' and 'Urban ReLeaf is looking for passionate residents to join a citizen science project that tracks where Riga feels hottest, and helps plan a greener, cooler future for all.' The section 'What's It All About?' follows, with three bullet points: 'We're measuring urban heat islands, these are places in the city that get uncomfortably hot.', 'You'll use portable sensors and a mobile app to collect data whilst walking.', and 'Your input will support smarter city planning and help fight climate change, right here in Riga.'

Why Join?

- Contribute to real solutions for a more liveable, sustainable city.
- Learn about climate and urban design through **free talks, walks, and community events.**
- Connect with neighbours, NGOs, and others shaping the future of our city.

Who Can Join?

We're especially looking for:

- Residents of central Riga
- Neighbourhood associations and NGOs
- Anyone who works or spends time outdoors in the city centre

Who Can Join?

We're especially looking for:

- Residents of central Riga
- Neighbourhood associations and NGOs
- Anyone who works or spends time outdoors in the city centre

When?

Data collection takes place from **June – August 2025**
Sign up now so we can get you the tools and info you need!

Get Involved

Fill out the form and we'll be in touch with next steps!

Applications must be submitted by 11th June.

Apply here

Take a step towards a greener city!

Join the Community
Science Project!

*Adopt a sensor and help
map heat island and
thermal discomfort!*

Find
out more

@releafcities #releafcities

Appendix E: Application form to fill in to become a researcher of heat islands (TRH sensors)

1. sadaļa no 2

Pieteikums piedalīties pilsētas termālā komforta kartēšanā

Rīgas plānošanas reģions projekta "Urban ReLeaf – Iedzīvotāju virzītas datu ekosistēmas pārejai uz iekļaujošu un zaļu pilsētvidi" ietvaros aicina iedzīvotājus piedalīties jau otrajā pilsētvides kvalitātes vērtēšanas aktivitātē. Pirmā – gaisa kvalitātes mērījumu veikšana jau veiksmīgi norit pateicoties iedzīvotāju, kā arī valsts un pašvaldību institūciju ieinteresētībai un atsaucībai. Šajā vasarā veicam otro kolektīvo aktivitāti pilsētvides kvalitātes vērtēšanai, kurā kartēsim Rīgas pilsētas termālo komfortu, vācot un novērojot temperatūras un mitruma rādītājus Rīgas pilsētas centrā un tam tuvējās apkaimēs. Lai kļūtu par šīs aktivitātes dalībnieku, aicinām aizpildīt zemāk pievienoto aptauju, kas palīdzēs mums novērtēt, vai esi piemērots plānotās aktivitātes īstenošanai.

Pamatojoties uz Jūsu sniegtajām atbildēm, novērtēsim, vai no mums pieejamiem 80 sensoriem varēsim piešķirt Jums vienu uz 2025. gada vasaras periodu.

Pieteikšanās atvērta no 23. maija - 11. jūnijam!

Informācija par personas datu apstrādi saistībā ar anketu:

Apstrādes nolūki, kam paredzēti personas dati, apstrādes tiesiskais pamats un ilgums:

Jūsu personas datu apstrādes nolūks ir saziņa par Jūsu turpmāk anketā norādīto iesaistes veidu projektā. Tiesiskais pamats – Jūsu sniegta piekrišana, atbilstoši Vispārīgās datu aizsardzības regulas 6.panta 1.punkta a) apakšpunktam, kas sniegta brīvi, konkrēti un apzināti. Apstrādes ilgums - līdz piekrišanas atsaukšanai vai līdz pētījuma izstrādes beigām.

Informējam, ka Jūs jebkurā brīdī variet atsaukt savu piekrišanu datu apstrādei, rakstot uz e-pastu: nora.gagane@riga.lv

Informējam, ka Jūs atbildiet par pareizu un precīzu savu datu iesniegšanu, kā arī informējam, ka trešo personu datu iesniegšana nav pieļaujama un var tikt uzskatīta par tiesību aktu pārkāpumu.

Personas datu saņēmēji:

Dalībnieku personas datus apstrādās tikai Rīgas plānošanas reģiona projekta "Urban ReLeaf" 3 darbinieki.

Jūsu vārds, uzvārds? *

Īsās atbildes teksts

Jūsu telefona numurs? *

Īsās atbildes teksts

Vai vēlaties kā savu e-pastu norādīt šo, caur kuru pašlaik pildāt aptauju? Ja nē, lūgums precizēt vēlamo epastu saziņai. *

Jā

Citas:

Jūsu vecuma grupa?

līdz 18

18 - 24

25 - 34

35 - 44

45 - 54

55 - 64

65+

Jūsu dzimums? *

Sieviete

Vīrietis

Neesmu binārs/a (ārpus binārā dzimumu iedalījuma)

Nevēlos atklāt / Atsakos atbildēt

Citas:

Kāds ir jūsu augstākais iegūtais izglītības līmenis? *

- Nav diploma
- Pamatizglītība
- Vidējā izglītība
- Tehniskā, arodizglītība vai profesionālā izglītība
- Bakalaura grāds
- Maģistra grāds
- Doktora grāds
- Es nevēlos atbildēt
- Citas:

Kurā, - s pilsētas apkaimē, -s Jūs visbiežāk un visvairāk pārvietojaties kājām? *

Īsās atbildes teksts
.....

Cik bieži Jūs dodaties pastaigā? *

- 1-2 reizes dienā
- 2-4 reizes nedēļā
- 1-2 reizes nedēļā
- Citas:

Vai Jūsu regulāro pastaigu ilgums ir vismaz 30 minūtes? *

- Jā
- Nē
- Citas:

Apzināties, ka daudzi rīdzinieki vasaras mēdz pavadīt citviet, līdz ar to aicinām padomāt laicīgi par jūsu pieejamību un klātesamību šajā vasarā. *

Lūdzu, atzīmējiet, cik daudz laika šovasar plānojat pavadīt Rīgā!

- Visu vasaru kopumā plānoju pavadīt Rīgā
- Ārpus Rīgas atradīšos līdz 2 nedēļām
- Ārpus Rīgas atradīšos aptuveni no 2 nedēļām līdz mēnesim garu periodu
- Ārpus Rīgas atradīšos aptuveni mēnesi vai ilgāk
- Ārpus Rīgas atradīšos tikai nedēļas nogalēs un svētku dienās
- Nezinu, grūti pateikt
- Citas:

Vai Jūs esat ieinteresēts, -ta piedalīties projekta organizētās lekcijās, izziņošās pastaigās, un vēlētos saņemt informāciju par Rīgas pilsētā notiekošiem orientēšanās pasākumiem u.tml.? *

- Jā
- Nē
- Nezinu
- Citas:

Vai Jūs veselības stāvoklis ir piemērots 20 - 40 minūšu pastaigām karstos laikapstākļos, t.i. ap 25 - 35 grādu temperatūrā? *

- Pavisam noteikti - jā
- Domāju, ka jā
- Drīzāk, ka nē
- Noteikti, ka nē
- Nezinu
- Citas:

Īsi pamatojiet savu motivāciju dalībai termālā komforta kartēšanā!

Īsās atbildes teksts

.....

Lūdzu, atzīmējiet apgalvojumus, kuriem varat piekrist: *

- Pirms gada es pieteicos gaisa kvalitātes sensora adoptēšanai, tomēr paliku gaidītāju rezervistu sarakstā
- Pirms gada adoptēju gaisa kvalitātes sensoru, tas uzstādīts manā dzīves/darba vietā
- Esmu biedrs apkaimes biedrībā
- Esmu biedrs biedrībā "Zaļā brīvība"
- Esmu biedrs biedrībā "Pilsēta cilvēkiem"
- Man ir pieejams C-type kabelis ar lādētāju, kuru varēšu izmantot sensora uzlādei
- Man ir pieejami vairāki C-type kabeļi, un lieko varu aizdot kādam citam, ar nosacījumu, ka to saņemšu atp...
- Esmu suņa īpašnieks, un regulāri dodamies pastaigās pa Rīgas centra apkaimēm
- Citas:

Neatkarīgi no tā, vai Jūsu piedāvātā sensora vieta tiek apstiprināta, labprāt iepazītos un/vai dalītos tālāk ar projektā gūto informāciju. *

- Jā, esmu ieinteresēts saņemt aktuālo informāciju par projekta aktivitātēm Rīgas pilsētā
- Nē, neesmu ieinteresēts saņemt aktuālo informāciju par projekta aktivitātēm Rīgas pilsētā
- Citas:

Vēlos / varēšu piedalīties termālā komforta kartēšanas atklāšanas pasākumā 16.jūnijā, 18:00! *

- Jā
- Nē
- Nezinu

Paldies par Jūsu atbildēm, šeit ir brīva vieta Jūsu komentāriem, idejām, ieteikumiem!

Īsās atbildes teksts

.....